

Towards understanding aluminum sulfur batteries with imidazolium-based electrolytes: A phenomenological model

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A phenomenological model for Al-S batteries is developed.
- Discharge mechanisms of Al-S batteries with Imidazolium-based electrolytes.
- Precipitation routes for polysulfides in Al-S batteries at different current rates.
- Experimentally validated model predictions at different current rates.

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Aluminum sulfur batteries
Ionic liquid electrolytes
Polysulfides
Modeling and simulation

ABSTRACT

Aluminum sulfur batteries with ionic liquid electrolytes are promising next-generation energy storage devices due to the high abundance of both aluminium and sulfur. However, very little understanding of the discharge mechanism is currently available, which hampers their development. Herein, a mathematical model that considers the complex electrochemical reduction of the sulfide species as well as the formation of the various polysulfides is developed to describe the discharge performance and the reversibility of Al-S cells at different current densities. The model is validated with experimental data obtained from Swagelok cells composed of Al metal anode, S@CNT cathode, and EMIMCl-AlCl₃ ionic liquid electrolyte. The cells exhibited different discharge mechanisms and Al₂S₃ precipitation routes at the different current densities. The contact resistance between the composite electrode and the current collector was the main factor limiting the discharge performance at high current densities. The reversibility of the Al-S cells based on the formation of Al₂S₃ precipitates strongly depends on the operating current density. The developed model will serve as a tool for other researchers to enhance the electrochemical performance of aluminum sulfur batteries.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are by far the most utilized energy storage device for electronic and automotive applications due to their high energy and power density [1–3]. However, issues such as the cost and safety [4], availability of natural lithium resources [5,6], and the utilization of flammable organic solvents as electrolytes [7] have motivated researchers to turn to cheaper and highly abundant elements. Aluminum, an abundant element [8] with a theoretical specific and volumetric capacities of 2980 mAh g⁻¹ and 8046 mAh cm⁻³ has been identified as one of the most promising anodes for high energy density

batteries. Coupling aluminum with a non-expensive sulfur-based cathode and an easily processable ionic liquid (IL) electrolyte such as 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride (EMIMCl)-AlCl₃ results in a potential electrochemical reversible Al-S battery with a high theoretical specific energy and operating voltage of ca. 1300 Wh kg⁻¹ mAh g⁻¹ and 1.23 V, respectively [9–11]. However, the mechanisms underlying the discharge process of Al-S batteries with IL electrolyte are not well understood. In particular, the correlation between the current densities and the electrochemical performance has not been thoroughly investigated.

Unlike Al-S batteries, the discharging/charging mechanisms and the effect of the electrode design on the electrochemical performance of Li-S

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231254>

Received 2 December 2021; Received in revised form 23 February 2022; Accepted 2 March 2022

Available online 11 March 2022

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Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the Al-S with EMIMCl-AlCl₃ IL electrolyte cell modeled in this study and the various rate-determining steps. Note that the equations for the cathode side are simplified due to the complexity of the charge/discharge route. The whole set of balanced equation for the cathode side are given in Eqs. (4)–(12).

batteries have been intensively investigated both experimentally [10,12,13] and through mathematical modeling and simulation [14–16]. Mikhaylik et al. [14] quantitatively connected the self-discharge, charge/discharge efficiency, and overcharge protection to the chemistry and interaction of polysulfides with the Li metal anode by directly comparing their model predictions to experimental data. Kumaresan et al. [15] developed a mathematical model to explain the two-stage discharge profiles observed in Li-S cells. Therein, the effects of the variation in the porosity of the porous sulfur cathode and the separator due to the formation of Li₂S_x precipitates were included in the model. A more advanced microstructure resolved model was developed by Thangavel et al. [16] to study the impact of cathode design performance of Li-S cells. The model developed considered the mass transport of the solutes in the electrolyte between the mesopores within the carbon particles and inter-particle pores as well as the changes in the diffusion coefficient of the various species. Zhang, Marinescu and others developed simpler models designed to identify critical factors affecting the performance of commercially relevant Li-S cells [17–19]. Al-Mahmoud et al. developed a simple, experiment-validated model designed to predict the self discharge of Li-S cells [20]. All the above models were developed for Li-S batteries with organic solvent electrolytes. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no reports on the development of a pseudo-two-dimensional based electrochemical model for the discharge performance of an Al-S cell with IL electrolytes. This is partly due to the complexity and the lack of adequate information on the reaction mechanisms at the S/IL electrolyte interface.

Herein, a mathematical model that considers the mass transport and kinetics of the various reactions at the cathode/electrolyte and anode/electrolyte interfaces, and within the porous electrode and separator is developed to describe the discharge mechanisms of an Al-S cell with EMIMCl-AlCl₃ IL electrolyte. The various complex electrochemical and chemical reactions between the sulfide species and IL electrolyte at the cathode/electrolyte interface considered in this model were determined by density functional theory-based formation energy calculations [21]. The developed model is validated by comparing the model predictions with experimental data obtained from Swagelok cells composed of Al metal anode, S@CNT cathode and EMIMCl-AlCl₃ IL electrolyte. The validated model is used to evaluate the relevance of kinetic and transport properties on the discharge performance of Al-S cells at various current rates. In addition, the model is used to explain the reversibility of Al-S batteries at the different current densities based on the formation Al₂S₃ precipitates in S@CNT cathode.

2. Model development

The model designed in this work is for predicting the galvanostatic discharge performance of a S@CNT composite cathode, an Al anode and two Whatman GF/F glass microfiber separator assembled in a Swagelok cell. The porous part of the cathode and separator are filled with an EMIMCl-AlCl₃ (molar ratio of 1:1.5) IL electrolyte. The schematic representation of the Al-S cell and the relevant rate determining steps considered in the model equations are presented in Fig. 1. The model considers the individual steps of the reactions at the anode and the cathode during the discharge process.

The individual steps involved in the reactions at the aluminium anode are (i) the transport of AlCl₄⁻ species in the bulk electrolyte to the anode/electrolyte interface where it reacts with Al to produce Al₂Cl₇⁻ electroactive species, (ii) the charge transfer reaction between AlCl₄⁻ and Al at the anode/electrolyte interface, and (iii) the transport of Al₂Cl₇⁻ species from the anode/electrolyte interface to the bulk electrolyte. The reaction path can, thus, be sketched as follows:

where [AlCl₄⁻]_b and [AlCl₄⁻]_{a,i} are the AlCl₄⁻ species in the bulk electrolyte and at the anode/electrolyte interface, [Al₂Cl₇⁻]_{a,i} and [Al₂Cl₇⁻]_b are the Al₂Cl₇⁻ species at anode/electrolyte interface and in the bulk electrolyte, and *k_{f,1}* and *k_{b,1}* are the charge transfer reactions rate constants. An extensive amount of research has been conducted to characterize the reaction mechanism at the anode/electrolyte interface [22–24]. For Lewis acidic EMIMCl-AlCl₃ IL electrolyte, the Lewis acidic species (Al₂Cl₇⁻) are considered to be the electroactive species for Al stripping and plating based on experimental studies using chronoamperometric technique [23] and ²⁷Al NMR studies [22] according to the reaction,

The individual steps involved in the reaction at the sulfur cathode are (i) the dissolution of solid sulfur, S_{8(solid)}, into the electrolyte forming dissolved sulfur, S_{8(dissolved)}, (ii) the charge transfer and diffusion reactions producing the reduction of dissolved sulfur, S_{8(dissolved)}, into soluble polysulfides, S_n²⁻, at the cathode/electrolyte interface, (iii) the further reduction of polysulfides forming Al₂S₃, first as a soluble species, Al₂S_{3(dissolved)}, which then (iv) precipitates as solid product, Al₂S_{3(solid)}. The reaction path can be sketched as follows:

where S_{8(s)} and S_{8(int)} are the sulfur species in the solid bulk phase and at the interface, S_{n(int)}²⁻ are the sulfide species, and Al₂Cl₂S_n⁻ are the polysulfides at the cathode/electrolyte interface. All the species at the interface are assumed to be in the solution phase.

Recent Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations have shown that polysulfides are not present as uncoordinated species in Al-S battery electrolytes [21]. Instead, polysulfides are coordinated to aluminium electrolyte species, and, in particular, the most stable polysulfide species are those in which polysulfides act as bidentate ligands to aluminium ions, which are also coordinated to chloride anions. However, in this model we followed the approach of previously developed models for Li-S batteries [15,16] where these reactions are separated into electrochemical reduction of uncoordinated sulfide species and the chemical reaction of the reduced sulfide species with the electroactive species to reduce the complexity of the model and enhance the speed of

Table 1

Transport properties: charges of the species, z_k , radius, diffusivity, D_k and reference concentrations, $C_{k,ref}$, defined in Eqs. (18) and (19).

Species (k)	z_k	Radius (nm)	D_k (m^2s^{-1})	$C_{k,ref}$ ($mol\ m^{-3}$)
$Al_2Cl_7^-$	-1	0.46 ^[a]	3.65×10^{-11}	1960 ^[c]
$AlCl_4^-$	-1	0.31 ^[a]	5.42×10^{-11}	1960 ^[c]
$S_{8(soln)}$	0	0.39 ^[b]	5.10×10^{-11}	1.49 ^[e]
S_8^{2-}	-2	0.33 ^[b]	3.33×10^{-11}	2.20×10^{-5} [d]
S_4^{2-}	-2	0.51 ^[b]	4.10×10^{-11}	1.68×10^{-5} [d]
S_2^{2-}	-2	0.41 ^[b]	5.79×10^{-11}	1.10×10^{-5} [d]
S^{2-}	-2	0.29 ^[b]	9.34×10^{-11}	2.40×10^{-5} [d]
EMIM ⁺	+1	0.18 ^[a]	4.31×10^{-11}	3920 ^[c]

[a] Parameters obtained from literature [25].

[b] Parameters obtained from literature [26].

[c] Parameters based on experimental design.

[d] Fitting parameters.

[e] Parameters obtained from literature [27].

the predictions. The model includes the following electrochemical reduction reactions, which were identified by DFT calculations as the most likely reaction pathway:

The chemical reactions that occur alongside the electrochemical reduction reaction during the discharge process are assumed to be according to the following equations.

The polysulfides formed in Al-S batteries are assumed to have a very short lifetime and are thus always in the solution phase. Based on the DFT [21] calculations, the two lower polysulfides in Eqs. (10) and (11) react with the electroactive species at the cathode/electrolyte interface to form Al_2S_3 according to the following equation:

2.1. Governing equations—porous separator

The porous part of the separator is filled with IL electrolyte. The transport of the species in the IL electrolyte is assumed to be in the axial direction, and the material balance on the species, k is given by

$$\varepsilon_{sep} \frac{\partial c_k}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot N_k \quad [13]$$

where ε_{sep} is the porosity of the separator and c_k is the concentration of species k ($k = Al_2Cl_7^-, AlCl_4^-, S_{8(int)}, S_{8(int)}^{2-}, S_{4(int)}, S_{4(int)}^{2-}, S_{2(int)}, S_{2(int)}^{2-}$ and EMIM⁺). The flux N_k of the k species is assumed to be due to migration in the electric field and diffusion in the concentration gradient, with the ionic mobility described by the Nernst-Einstein equation, and is given by:

$$N_k = -\varepsilon_{sep} D_k \nabla c_k - z_k \frac{\varepsilon_{sep} D_k}{RT} F c_k \nabla \Phi_2 \quad [14]$$

where D_k is the diffusion coefficient of the k species, z_k is the charge number of species k , and Φ_2 is the potential in the liquid phase. The diffusion coefficients of the different electrolyte species were obtained using the Stokes-Einstein equation, which has been shown to produce results in good agreement with experiments in previous work in EMICl-AlCl₃ electrolytes [25]: $D_k = RT/6\pi N_A \eta r$, R is the gas constant (8.3145 J mol K), T is the absolute temperature (298 K in this case), N_A is Avogadro's number, η is the viscosity (13 mbar) [10] and r is the radius of the species. The transport properties and the reference concentrations are presented in Table 1.

2.2. Governing equations—porous cathode

The material balance on the individual species, k , in the multicomponent IL electrolyte in the porous cathode is given by

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_1 c_k}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot N_k + r_k - R_k \quad [15]$$

The rate of production/consumption r_k of species, k , due to the electrochemical reactions occurring at the cathode/IL electrolyte interface is directly related to the current densities of the individual electrochemical reactions in which a given specie is involved and is given as

$$r_k = -a \sum_j \frac{s_{k,j} (i_1)_j}{n_j F} \quad [16]$$

where a is the specific surface area of the porous cathode, n_j is the number of electrons involved in reaction j , i_1 is the current densities due to the electrochemical reaction, j and $s_{k,j}$ is the stoichiometric coefficient of the species in the electrochemical reactions, j , occurring at the surface of the anode and at the solid/electrolyte interface within the porous cathode. The rate of the individual electrochemical reactions, j , is given by the Butler-Volmer equation according to the form [16],

$$(i_1)_j = n_j q \left[(K_1^a)_j \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_{a,j} n_j F}{RT} \eta_j\right) - (K_1^c)_j \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha_{c,j} n_j F}{RT} \eta_j\right) \right] \quad [17]$$

where q is the charge number, K_1^a and K_1^c are the anodic and cathodic rate constants expressed based on transition-state theory as

$$(K_1^a)_j = \left(\frac{k_B T}{h}\right) A e^{-\left(\frac{E_{a,j}}{RT}\right)} \prod_{(k)} \left[\frac{c_k}{C_{ref,k}}\right]^{p_{(k),j}} \quad [18]$$

$$(K_1^c)_j = \left(\frac{k_B T}{h}\right) A e^{-\left(\frac{E_{c,j}}{RT}\right)} \prod_{(k)} \left[\frac{c_k}{C_{ref,k}}\right]^{q_{(k),j}} \quad [19]$$

where k_B denotes the Boltzmann constant, h denotes the Planck constant, T is the operating temperature, A is the area factor, and E_a denoted the energy barrier for the individual electrochemical reactions. It is assumed that the energy barrier for the forward and backward reactions are the same. $p_{(k),j}$ and $q_{(k),j}$ are the coefficients for the products and reactants involved in the electrochemical reactions, j . The overpotential η_j for the reaction j is expressed as

$$\eta_j = \Phi_1 - \Phi_2 - U_j - i_{film} R_{film} \quad [20]$$

Table 2

Table 2. Kinetics and thermodynamic properties: Activation energy $E_{a,j}$, standard reduction potential, U_j^0 , number of electrons, n_j , and transference numbers, α_a, α_c .

Reaction (j)	$E_{a,j}$ (J.mol ⁻¹)	U_j^0 (V)	n_j	α_a, α_c
2	14300 ^[a]	0	3	0.5
4	5400 ^[c]	1.01 ^[b]	2	0.5
5	18400 ^[c]	1.01 ^[b]	2	0.5
6	20529 ^[c]	1.00 ^[b]	2	0.5
7	21561 ^[c]	0.81 ^[b]	2	0.5

[a] Parameters obtained from literature [23].

[b] Assumed parameters based on experimental GITT data.

[c] Fitting parameters.

where Φ_1 is the potential in the solid phase, and R_{film} is the contact resistance between the composite electrode and the current collector. In this work, the R_{film} is used as a fitting parameter to fit the voltage profiles at different current rates. The equilibrium potential for any of the electrochemical reactions is expressed in a general form as

$$U_j = U_j^0 - \frac{RT}{n_j F} \sum_k s_{(k)(j)} \ln[(c)_k(f)_k] \quad [21]$$

where c is the concentration of the species involved in the electrochemical reaction and f its activity coefficient assumed to be 1, and U_j^0 is the standard potential of the electrochemical reaction, j . The equilibrium potential for the stripping and plating of Al according to the electrochemical reaction in Eq. (2) is determined by the Nernst's equation and is expressed as

$$U_{(2)} = \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \left\{ \frac{\left[\frac{c_{(Al_2Cl_7^-)} f_{(Al_2Cl_7^-)}}{c_{(AlCl_4^-)} f_{(AlCl_4^-)}} \right]^4}{\left[\frac{c_{(AlCl_4^-)} f_{(AlCl_4^-)}}{c_{(AlCl_2S_8^{2-})} f_{(AlCl_2S_8^{2-})}} \right]^7} \right\} \quad [22]$$

Following previous work on Li-S batteries [15], the equilibrium potential at the cathode is determined based on $S_{2(int)}^{2-}/S_{(int)}^{2-}$ reduction reaction in Eq. (7) as

$$U_{(7)} = U_{(7)}^0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left\{ \frac{\left[\frac{c_{(S_2^{2-})} f_{(S_2^{2-})}}{c_{(S^{2-})} f_{(S^{2-})}} \right]^2}{\left[\frac{c_{(S^{2-})} f_{(S^{2-})}}{c_{(S^{2-})} f_{(S^{2-})}} \right]^2} \right\} \quad [23]$$

The cell voltage depends on the equilibrium potential in the anode and the cathode, the overpotential and is expressed as

$$U_{cell} = U_{(7)} - U_{(2)} + \eta_j \quad [24]$$

The parameters used for the kinetic and electrochemical reactions are presented in Table 2.

Following the assumption of electroneutrality, the charges leaving the solution phase must be equal to the charges entering the solid phase according to the expression

$$\nabla \cdot i_s + \nabla \cdot i_2 = 0 \quad [25]$$

where i_s denotes the current density in the solid phase, and i_2 denotes the current density in the solution phase. The charge transfer in the solid phase is governed by Ohm's law

$$i_s = -\sigma \nabla \Phi_1 \quad [26]$$

where σ is conductivity of the cathode. The current density in the solution phase is given by

$$i_2 = F \sum_k z_k N_k \quad [27]$$

Charges can enter or leave the solution phase only by the electrochemical reaction at the cathode/IL electrolyte interface, and this

Table 3

Parameters for the polysulfide formation in Eq. (31) and elemental sulfur dissolution reaction in Eq. (30).

Species (z)	k_z ^[a] (mol ⁻² m ⁶ s ⁻¹)	\bar{V}_z ^[a] (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$K_{sp,i}$ (mol m ⁻³)
AlCl ₂ S _{8(soln)} ⁻	4.0×10^{-21}	–	–
AlCl ₂ S _{4(soln)} ⁻	4.0×10^{-21}	–	–
AlCl ₂ S _{2(soln)} ⁻	4.0×10^{-21}	–	–
AlCl ₂ S ⁻ _(soln)	2.3×10^{-7}	–	–
S _{8(s)}	0.1 s^{-1}	1.24×10^{-4}	1.49 ^[e]

[a] Assumed parameters.

[e] Parameters obtained from literature [27].

achieved through the following charge constraint equations

$$\nabla \cdot i_2 = a \sum_j (i_1)_j \quad [28]$$

The rate of production/consumption of species k , R_k , due to dissolution/chemical/precipitation reaction, i is given by

$$R_k = \sum_i \gamma_{k,i} R_i' + \sum_z \gamma_{k,z} R_z^* \quad [29]$$

where R_i' is the rate of dissolution of solid species i ($S_{8(s)}$), R_z^* is the chemical rate of formation of the polysulfide species z ($AlCl_2S_{8(soln)}^-$, $AlCl_2S_{4(soln)}^-$, $AlCl_2S_{2(soln)}^-$, and $AlCl_2S_{(soln)}^-$), $\gamma_{k,i}$ and $\gamma_{k,z}$ are the number of moles of ionic species k in the solid species i and polysulfide species z , respectively. The rate of precipitation of the solid species i is assumed to be kinetically controlled and is given by [15].

$$R_i' = k_i \varepsilon_i \left(\prod_i c_i^{\gamma_{k,i}} - K_{sp,i} \right) \quad [30]$$

where k_i , ε_i and $K_{sp,i}$ are the rate constant, volume fraction of the species in the solid phase, and the solubility of the precipitate i . The rate of production of the polysulfide species z is given by

$$R_z^* = k_z \prod_z c_z^{\gamma_{k,z}} \quad [31]$$

The parameters for the formation/dissolution reactions are presented in Table 3.

The rate of formation of Al_2S_3 at the cathode/IL electrolyte interface is assumed to be an irreversible parallel reaction, and it is described by the cathodic part of the Butler-Volmer equation according to

$$(i_1)_p = -n_p q \left[(K_1^c)_p \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha_c F}{RT} \eta_p\right) \right] \quad [32]$$

where K_1^c is the rate constant taking from the transition-state theory and η_p is the overpotential for the parasitic side reaction. Above the solubility limit, which was assumed to be 21 mM [27], $Al_2S_{3(sol)}$ begins to precipitate into $Al_2S_{3(s)}$. The dissolution of $S_{8(s)}$ and the precipitation of $Al_2S_{3(s)}$ lead to a decrease and an increase in the porosity of the cathode, respectively. The changes in the concentration of Al_2S_3 species in the solution and solid phase is given, respectively by

$$\frac{\partial(c_{k_p})}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{n_p F} a i_p \times (c_{k_p} < c_{\max,k_p}) \quad [33]$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{k_p(s)}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{n_p F} a i_p \times (c_{k_p} \geq c_{\max,k_p}) \quad [34]$$

where c_{\max,k_p} is the solubility of Al_2S_3 and n_p is the number of electrons involved in the parasitic reaction. The subscript k_p represents $Al_2S_{3(s)}$ precipitate species. The volume fraction of $S_{8(s)}$ and $Al_2S_{3(s)}$ is dependent on the molar volume of \bar{V}_{k_s} and is expressed respectively as

Table 4
Parameters for the parallel reaction (Eq. (12)).

Symbol	Description	Units	Value ^[a]
$E_{a,p}$	Activation energy	J mol ⁻¹	2000
U_p^0	Equilibrium potential	V	0.1
n_p	Number of electrons	-	2
ρ_p	Density	kg m ⁻³	542.68
M_p	Molecular weight	g mol ⁻¹	150.16
$c_{max,kp}$	Maximum concentration	mol m ⁻³	7.0 ^[b]
k_{ads}	Adsorption rate constant	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	6.5×10^{-6}

[a] Assumed parameters.

[b] Parameters obtained from literature [27].

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{k_s}}{\partial t} = -R_{k_s}^* \bar{V}_{k_s} \quad [35]$$

$$\varepsilon_{k_p} = (c_{k_p(s)} - c_{k_p(s),0}) \times \bar{V}_{k_s} \quad [36]$$

The subscript k_s represents $S_{8(s)}$ species. The parameters for the parallel reaction (Eq. (12)) for the formation of $Al_2S_3(s)$ are presented in Table 4.

The precipitation of $Al_2S_3(s)$ in the cathode decreases the active interfacial area between the cathode and the IL electrolyte. The specific surface area in the cathode is assumed to vary according to the expression

$$a = a_0 \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_{k_p} - \varepsilon_{k_s}}{\varepsilon_0} \right]^{1.5} \quad [37]$$

where a_0 and ε_0 are the initial specific surface area and porosity of the cathode after impregnation with S. As the $Al_2S_3(s)$ precipitates, it is assumed in this model that they are being deposited either on the bare CNT after the dissolution of solid $S_{8(s)}$ or on the $S_{8(s)}$ depending on the current rate. A schematic representation of this mechanism is shown in Fig. 2.

The effect of the increase in the coverage and thickness of the precipitated $Al_2S_3(s)$ is considered by assuming that the rate constant for the electrochemical reaction j is a function of the coverage, $\theta_{Al_2S_3}$ and the thickness, δ_{film} [28,29].

$$\left(K_{1,eff}^i \right)_j = \left(K_{1,\theta=0}^i \right)_j (1 - \theta_{Al_2S_3}) + \left(K_1^i \right)_j e^{-\beta \delta_{film}} \theta_{Al_2S_3} \quad [38]$$

where $K_{1,\theta=0}^i$ is rate constant for the electrochemical reaction obtained from the transition-state theory, K_1^i is the rate constant of the electron transfer through the $Al_2S_3(s)$ film and β is the tunneling barrier coefficient. The evolution of the coverage depends on the rate of the formation of the $Al_2S_3(s)$ precipitates and the rate of adsorption of $Al_2S_3(s)$ onto the

surface of the bare CNT or $S_{8(s)}$, k_{ads} according to the expression

$$\theta_{Al_2S_3} = \frac{(-i_1)_p}{Fk_{ads}} \quad [39]$$

The film thickness, δ_{film} is given by

$$\delta_{film} = \left[\frac{(1 - \varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_b + \varepsilon_{k_p})}{\pi L_{CNT} \rho_{p,CNT}} \right]^{1/2} - R_{CNT} \quad [40]$$

where L_{CNT} , R_{CNT} , $\rho_{p,CNT}$ are the length, radius, and density of the CNT respectively, and ε_b is the volume fraction of the binding component.

The discharge capacity available from the cathode after a complete constant current discharge, Q_{dch} and the capacity due to the formation of $Al_2S_3(s)$, Q_s are given respectively as

$$Q_{dch} = \int_0^{t=t_{cc}} \varepsilon_{S_{8(s)}} \sigma \frac{\partial \Phi_1}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L_{sep}+L_{pos}} dt \quad [41]$$

$$Q_s = \int_0^{t=t_{cc}} (i_1)_p dt \quad [42]$$

where $\varepsilon_{S_{8(s)}}$ is the volume fraction of the Sulfur in the cathode, σ is the conductivity of the cathode, Φ_1 is the potential in the solid phase, and $(i_1)_p$ is the current density due to the formation of $Al_2S_3(s)$. L_{sep} and L_{pos} are the thickness of the separator and cathode respectively.

2.3. Boundary and initial conditions

There 10 boundary conditions required at the cathode/current collector interface, ($x = L_{sep} + L_{pos}$). Eight for the concentration of the species and one each for the potential in the solid, Φ_1 and liquid phase, Φ_2 . The flux of each species k ($k = Al_2Cl_7^-$, $AlCl_4^-$, $S_{8(soln)}$, S_8^{2-} , S_4^{2-} , S_2^{2-} , S^{2-} and EMIM⁺) is set to zero

$$N_k = 0 \quad [43]$$

In addition, at the cathode/current collector interface, the current density in the solid phase is equal to the external current density applied to the cell and hence the current density in the solution phase at this boundary is equal to zero

$$-\sigma \cdot \nabla \cdot \Phi_1 = I_{app} \quad [44]$$

$$i_2 = 0 \quad [45]$$

where I_{app} is the applied constant current.

At separator/cathode interface, ($x = L_{sep}$), there are 10 boundary conditions because of the 10 differential equations on either side of this interface. The flux of each of the species, k is continuous and can be

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of $Al_2S_3(s)$ precipitation routes under low current (a) and high current (b) regimes. The precipitation routes were obtained by fitting the model predictions to the experimental data.

Table 5
Experimental design parameters.

Name	Symbol	Units	Value
Cathode thickness	L_{pos}	μm	50
Separator thickness	L_{sep}	μm	620
Cathode porosity	ϵ	–	0.85
Separator porosity	ϵ_{sep}	–	0.89
Radius of CNT	R_{CNT}	nm	6
Particle number density	$\rho_{p,CNT}$	m^{-3}	5.84×10^{19}
Conductivity of cathode	σ	S m^{-1}	10^7
Length of CNT	L_{CNT}	μm	10
Radius of cathode	R_c	mm	5.5
Volume fraction of Sulfur	ϵ_{ks}	–	0.0865
Volume fraction of binder	ϵ_{kb}	–	0.002

expressed as

$$N_{k,separator} = N_{k,cathode} \quad [46]$$

The current at the separator/cathode interface is carried by the solution phase and the solution phase current density is continuous. Thus, the solid phase current density at this interface is zero

$$-\sigma \cdot \nabla \cdot \Phi_1 = 0 \quad [48]$$

The boundary condition above indicates that the assumption that there is no accumulation of any of the sulfide or polysulfide or the electroactive species at the separator/cathode interface, and there is no transfer of the species across the cathode/current collector interface.

At the anode/separator interface ($x = 0$), the flux of all the species, k are zero except that of the reacting species Al_2Cl_7^- and AlCl_4^- . Moreover, since the flux of all the species are zero except the reacting species at this interface, the solution phase current density is given by Eq. (50).

$$N_k = 0 \text{ and } N_{1,2} = \frac{(i_1)_j}{F} \quad [49]$$

$$\Phi_1 = 0 \text{ and } i_e = FN_{1,2} \quad [50]$$

where $N_{1,2}$ is the flux for Al_2Cl_7^- and AlCl_4^- , and $(i_1)_j$ is the current density at the surface of the Al anode expressed by the Butler Volmer Eq. (17).

At the beginning of the discharge process ($t = 0$) the initial concentration of the all the species, k is set to the reference concentration, $c_{k,ref}$ values in Table 1. This is mathematically represented as

$$c_k = c_{k,ref} \text{ at } t = 0 \text{ and for all } x \geq 0 \quad [51]$$

The developed model equations were solved using the tertiary current distribution module, and global Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) and Differential Algebraic Equations (DAEs) module in COMSOL Multiphysics. These two modules provide the required governing equations and boundary conditions needed for this study. The parameters used in the model are given in Tables 1–5.

3. Experimental section

3.1. Materials

The reagents used for electrode preparation were sulfur (Aldrich, 100-mesh), multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNT, 98% basis, Sigma-Aldrich), polyethylene oxide (PEO, 8,000,000 M_w Sigma-Aldrich), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, Aldrich) and a premade 10 vol% solution of ethanol (Fisher, $\geq 99.8\%$ analytical grade) in deionized water. A pre-cut piece of Mo foil (25 μm thickness, $\geq 99.9\%$ trace metals basis, Sigma-Aldrich) was used as a substrate for these electrodes. The ionic liquid electrolyte 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride-aluminium chloride (EMIMCl-AlCl₃, 1:1.5 M ratio) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Fig. 3. Model best fit to experimental data of Al-S cells discharged at different current densities in an EMIMCl-AlCl₃ ionic liquid electrolyte. The current densities 50 mA g⁻¹, 167 mA g⁻¹ and 334 mA g⁻¹ corresponds to C/33, C/10 and C/5 respectively.

3.2. Electrode preparation

Sulfur and CNT were mixed (in a mass ratio of 2:1, sulfur:carbon) by agate pestle and mortar for 15 min. In a vial, 6 mg of PEO and 6 mg of PVP were dissolved in a 1.8 ml solution containing 10 vol% ethanol in water using a magnetic stirring bar. The S/CNT mixture was then added to the PEO/PVP binder solution and stirred for 2 h. A pre-cut piece of Mo foil was lightly wiped with SiC paper (wiped 20 times), cleaned using ethanol, then coated with ink using a doctor blade coater. After the ethanol and water evaporates off, the coated electrode sheet was punched into round discs ($\varnothing = 11$ mm, Hohsen hand-held precision punch). These were transferred into a Büchi tube and dried at room temperature (typically, 20–25 °C), under vacuum for no less than 2 days. After moving the electrodes to an Ar-filled glovebox ($\text{H}_2\text{O} \leq 4.0$ ppm, $\text{O}_2 \leq 0.1$ ppm), the electrodes were weighed (OHAUS Adventurer™, AR0640) before use to calculate the precise amount of active material, and therefore, calculate the correct current to be applied. The average coating thickness was 49 μm and average sulfur loading was 0.90 mg_S cm⁻².

3.3. Electrochemical characterisation

Electrochemical testing was conducted using a VMP3 potentiostat (Biologic Science Instruments) with constructed cells placed in a Memmert climatic chamber set to 25 °C. C-rate experiments used galvanostatic cycling with potential limitation (GCPL), applying an upper and lower voltage limit of 1.85 and 0.05 V respectively. Three different applied specific currents (normalized by the mass of sulfur) were used: 50, 167.2, 334.4 mA g⁻¹ (C/33, C/10, C/5, respectively). Cells were left at rest at the open circuit potential for 6 h before being discharged (to 0.05 V) and then charged (to 1.85 V), for ten cycles. A different cell was used for each specific current value, in order to be able to separate the effect of the current value and of the cycle number, but all the cells were assembled in the same way and the differences in sulfur loading of the electrodes were lower than 7.5%. The experimental procedure and electrode design parameters used in this work are similar to those reported previously [10].

Fig. 4. Concentration profile of the electroactive species Al_2Cl_7^- and AlCl_4^- , (a) and (b) at 50 mA g^{-1} , (c) and (d) at 167 mA g^{-1} , and (e) and (f) at 334 mA g^{-1} , respectively. The dash line separates the separator from the cathode, $x = 0$ is the Al anode/electrolyte interface, and $x = 1$ is the cathode/current-collector interface.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Model validation

To validate the developed model, the model predictions were fitted to experimental data obtained from Swagelok cells composed of Al anode, $S@CNT$ cathode, and an IL electrolyte at a current density of 167 mA g^{-1} (equivalent to a C-rate of C/10). The model predictions were made using the parameters in Tables 1–4 and the cell design parameters in Table 5. Owing to the lack of enough information on the electrochemical reactions, the activation energies of the individual reactions,

E_{aj} , and the reference concentration of sulfide species, $c_{k,ref}$, were treated as fitting parameters for fitting the model predictions to the experimental data at a current density of 167 mA g^{-1} . The model best fit is presented in Fig. 3. The validated model was used to predict the voltage profile of the cells at a lower and a higher current density of 50 mA g^{-1} and 334 mA g^{-1} , respectively, and fitted to their respective experimental data. The model overestimated the discharge capacity at the lower current rate and underestimated it at a higher current rate. In order to resolve this issue, the rate constant for the formation of $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^-_{(soln)}$ was also treated as a fitting parameter. A lower rate constant

Fig. 5. Volume fraction and concentration of sulfide species as a function of discharge time at a current density of (a) 50 mA g^{-1} , (b) 167 mA g^{-1} and (c) 334 mA g^{-1} .

of $1.4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ m}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was estimated from fitting the model prediction to the experimental data at the lower current density of 50 mA g^{-1} and a higher value of $9.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ m}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was estimated for that at a current density of 334 mA g^{-1} . The validated model also overestimated the cell voltage at the higher current density. Hence a film resistance, R_{film} ($15.4 \text{ } \Omega \text{ m}^2$), which is defined as the resistance between the composite electrode and the current collector [30] was used to fit the cell voltage at the various current densities presented in Fig. 3. There was a high correlation between the model predictions and the experimental data indicating the ability of the model to replicate the discharge characteristics of Al-S batteries with an EMIMCl-AlCl₃ ionic liquid electrolyte.

4.2. Model predictions

The concentration profiles of Al_2Cl_7^- and AlCl_4^- ions across the thickness of the cell at various times during the discharge process at a constant current density of 50 mA g^{-1} are shown in Fig. 4a and b respectively while those for a constant current density of 167 mA g^{-1} and 334 mA g^{-1} are shown in Fig. 4c and d, and 4e and 4f respectively. At the surface of the Al anode, AlCl_4^- ions in the bulk electrolyte are consumed in the electrochemical reaction in Eq. (2) to produce Al_2Cl_7^- ions. Hence, the initial concentration of Al_2Cl_7^- ions increased during the early stages of the discharge process while those of AlCl_4^- ions decreased at the surface of the anode ($x = 0$) for all the current densities. However, the concentration of the Al_2Cl_7^- ions decreased and those of AlCl_4^- ions increased after a time of ca. 50000 s, 5000 s and 4000 s for the discharge

current density of 50 mA g^{-1} (Fig. 4a and b), 167 mA g^{-1} (Fig. 4c and d), and 334 mA g^{-1} (Fig. 4e and f), respectively at the surface of the anode. The reason for such behavior exhibited by the electroactive species at the surface of the anode is that the predominant sulfide ions produced in the cathode at the early stages of the discharge process are $\text{S}_{8(\text{int})}^{2-}$ (Eq. (4)) and $\text{S}_{4(\text{int})}^{2-}$ (Eq. (5)). These sulfide ions are consumed to produce $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_{8(\text{int})}^-$ and $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_{4(\text{int})}^-$ polysulfides at a very low rate through the chemical reactions given in Eqs. (8) and (9). Since the rate of consumption of these sulfide ions is very low and almost negligible, the sulfide ions remains in the electrolyte and hence their concentration increases. Eventually, the Al_2Cl_7^- ions produced at the anode during this stage of the discharge process also remain in the electrolyte resulting in an increase in its concentration and vice versa for the AlCl_4^- ions. As the discharge proceeds, the cell potential decreases. The predominant sulfide ions switch to $\text{S}_{2(\text{int})}^{2-}$ and $\text{S}_{(\text{int})}^{2-}$ which are produced through the electrochemical reactions given by Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) with a relatively lower standard potential than that of Eqs. (4) and (5). These sulfide ions are consumed to produce $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_{2(\text{int})}^-$ and $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_{(\text{int})}^-$ respectively at a relatively higher rate than the polysulfides produced at the early stages of the discharge process. The production of the polysulfides in the chemical reactions involves the consumption of the Al_2Cl_7^- ions and production of AlCl_4^- ions, thus the decrease in the concentration of the Al_2Cl_7^- ions and an increase in that of AlCl_4^- ions at the later stages of the discharge process at the various current densities as illustrated in Fig. 4.

As expected, the concentration profile of Al_2Cl_7^- and AlCl_4^- ions at the lower current density of 50 mA g^{-1} in Fig. 4a and b did not show any significant gradient across the cell at a given discharge time. However,

Fig. 6. Evolution of cathode porosity and volume fraction of solid precipitates at a discharge current density of (a) 50 mA g⁻¹ (b) 167 mA g⁻¹ and (c) 334 mA g⁻¹.

they exhibited a significant gradient across the cell at a current density of 167 mA g⁻¹ (Fig. 4c and d) and 334 mA g⁻¹ (Fig. 4e and f). Nevertheless, the concentrations of the electrochemically active species were high enough at the end of the discharge at all the discharge current densities. Thus, the cells did not exhibit any solution-phase diffusion limitation issues at the given current densities.

Fig. 5 shows the variation in the average concentrations of the various sulfides in the cathode at different discharge current densities with time. These variations in the concentrations provide an in-depth understanding about the mechanisms that occur in the Al-S batteries at different current densities during the discharge process. From Fig. 5, the shape of the concentration profile of the sulfide species differs for each current density indicating different discharge mechanisms. Based on the average concentrations of the sulfide species at a low current density of 50 mA g⁻¹ in Fig. 5a, the discharge process can be divided into two main parts. During the early stages of the discharge process (part 1), the dissolved elemental sulfur at the solid/IL electrolyte interface ($S_{8(int)}$) is reduced in the cathode to $S_{8(int)}^{2-}$ which is further reduced to $S_{4(int)}^{2-}$. Owing to the kinetically controlled dissolution of $S_{8(s)}$ to $S_{8(int)}$, the solution phase is replenished with elemental sulfur $S_{8(int)}$ and the concentration of $S_{8(int)}$ remains constant at the solubility limit of 1.49 mol m⁻³ until all the elemental sulfur in the solid phase, $S_{8(s)}$ is utilized. At the later stages of the discharge process (part 2), all the elemental sulfur in the solid phase, $S_{8(s)}$ is utilized, and the concentration of $S_{8(int)}$ decreases. This leads to a sharp reduction in the concentration of $S_{8(int)}^{2-}$ and slight decrease in the concentration of $S_{4(int)}^{2-}$ because they are electrochemically reduced to $S_{2(int)}^{2-}$ and $S_{(int)}^{2-}$. The rate of electrochemical production of $S_{2(int)}^{2-}$ and $S_{(int)}^{2-}$ increases rapidly during the second part of the discharge process until a maximum concentration of

$S_{(int)}^{2-}$ at which the electrochemical reaction stops. The maximum concentration of $S_{(int)}^{2-}$ was obtained by fitting the model predicted voltage profile to that of the experimental data. The mechanism exhibited here is similar to that reported for the first two stages of Li-S in Refs. [15,16].

For the cells discharged at higher current densities of 167 mA g⁻¹ (Figs. 5b) and 334 mA g⁻¹ (Fig. 5c), the shape of the predicted concentration profile of the sulfide species was different from those predicted at the lower current density of 50 mA g⁻¹ (Fig. 5a). Fig. 5b and c shows that the discharge process exhibited just the first part of the mechanism described above for the lower discharge current density. This is because the dissolution of the elemental sulfur in the solid phase, $S_{8(s)}$ is kinetically controlled and is not influenced by the value of the applied current density. Thus at a lower discharge time, only ca. 73.5% and 30.32% of the total elemental sulfur was utilized at a discharge current density of 167 mA g⁻¹ and 334 mA g⁻¹, respectively. The maximum concentration of $S_{(int)}^{2-}$ required for the completion of the electrochemical process for the cells discharged at the high current densities was lower than that of the cells discharged at the lower current density.

The evolution of the cathode porosity and the volume fraction of the solid precipitates are presented in Fig. 6. During the discharge process, the elemental sulfur in the solid phase dissolves into the electrolyte according to Eq. (3) resulting in an increase in the cathode porosity as shown in Fig. 6. The rate of dissolution is assumed to be constant for all the current densities, thus the cathode porosities increased at the same rate. For the cells discharged at a current density of 50 mA g⁻¹ (Fig. 6a), all the elemental sulfur in solid phase dissolved into the electrolyte at a discharge capacity of ca. 600 mAh g⁻¹. The complete dissolution of elemental sulfur into the electrolyte at this discharge current density

Fig. 7. Thickness and concentration of Al_2S_3 as a function of discharge capacity at a current density of (a) 50 mA g_s^{-1} , (b) 167 mA g_s^{-1} and (c) 334 mA g_s^{-1} .

predicted by the model has been reported experimentally by Lampkin et al. [10]. After the discharge capacity of ca. 600 mAh g_s^{-1} , the cathode porosity begins to decrease owing to the increase in the volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ precipitates. However, for the cells discharged at 167 mA g_s^{-1} (Fig. 6b), the cathode porosity began to decrease at discharge capacity of ca. $1000 \text{ mAh g}_s^{-1}$ even though there was still some elemental sulfur in the solid phase. Thus the $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ precipitates deposits on thin sulfur layer on the CNT. These precipitation routes were obtained after fitting the model predictions to the experimental discharge profiles and presented in Fig. 2. Unlike the cells discharge at the two lower current densities, the porosity of the cells discharged at 334 mA g_s^{-1} (Fig. 6c) did not decrease because the time for discharge and the current density was not enough for the precipitation of $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$.

The predicted concentration and thickness of Al_2S_3 are presented in Fig. 7 for cells discharged at different current densities. The rate constant for the formation of the $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ was constant for all the current densities. However, the evaluated rate of production of $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_{(\text{int})}^-$ (Eq. (11)), based on the fitting of the model predicted voltage profile to the experimental data, varied for the different current densities. Even though the rate of production of the reactants was low for cells discharged at a 50 mA g_s^{-1} , the longer discharge time lead to the formation of thicker $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ precipitates (Fig. 7a), as compared to that of the cells discharged at 167 mA g_s^{-1} (Fig. 7b). The concentration of the $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(\text{sol})$ produced at a current density of 334 mA g_s^{-1} did not reach the solubility limit, and thus no $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ precipitates were formed, as shown in Fig. 7c.

5. Conclusion

A mathematical model based on the dilute solution theory was

developed to describe the discharge performance of Al-S batteries with EMIMCl-AlCl₃ IL electrolyte at different current densities. The discharge mechanisms considered in the model was based on DFT formation energy calculations. The effects of the formation and precipitation of Al_2S_3 species as well as the dissolution of elemental sulfur on the cathode porosity, rate of electrochemical reaction, and available cathode active surface area was included in the model as the limiting factor for the discharge performance. The cells exhibited different discharge mechanisms at the various current densities with the dissolution of elemental sulfur, S_8 and the electrochemical reduction of $\text{S}_{2(\text{int})}^{2-}$ to $\text{S}_{(\text{int})}^{2-}$ being the rate determining reactions. Based on the validation of the model predictions with the experimental data, the contact resistance between the composite sulfur electrode and the current collector was the main factor responsible for the reduced discharge capacity of Al-S batteries at high current densities. The thickness of the $\text{Al}_2\text{S}_3(s)$ precipitates was high for cells discharge at a lower current density whiles at high current density no precipitates were formed. The current collector's high current rate performance can be improved by surface modification, enhancing the electric contact. In such a way, the developed model will provide more rational design of Al-S cells with improved energy and power density.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Williams Agyei Appiah: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **He Li:** Experiments, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **John Lampkin:** Experiments, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Juan Maria García-Lastra:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support for this work from the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 FET-OPEN project AMAPOLA projects (grant agreements No. 951902). We also thank Prof. Nuria Garcia-Araez for her constructive comments and discussions on this work and most importantly the experimental section.

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